

Problems Confronting Government Industries in A Depressed Economy in Nigeria

Dr. D.E. EBINGA, PhD Business Education
EBONYI STATE UNIVERSITY, ABAKALIKI

Abstract:- The economic situation in Nigeria in present day leaves much to be desired. This study focused on the problems affecting government owned industries in a depressed economy in Nigeria. The study was conducted in Ezzangbo Block Industry. Five (5) research questions were formulated to guide the study and data were gathered using structured questionnaire and oral interview. The population of the study consisted of the 120 workers of the industry which also formed the sample. This is because the population was too small, therefore there was no sampling technique. Data were analyzed and interpreted using mean statistics. The result of the investigations include financial constant, inadequate infrastructural facilities, neglect by the government and management styles as the major problems facing the industry. Managerial laxity; lack of incentives to workers and poor trained personnel are how managerial problems affected the study. More so, the study showed that the technical problems affecting the industry included the use of inferior spare parts, loading and off loading and break down of plants and machinery. Operational problems affecting production process includes power outage, articulated vehicle, deteriorating nature of plant and machinery and power operating skills of machines in the industry. The study lastly revealed that government agencies seldom supervise the activities of the manager recruitment and training of staff and appointment of competent managers as the extent to which government has reacted towards solving managerial problems of the industry. The researcher provision of financial assistance by the government for the industry. Supervision of activities of the industry and privatization of the industry.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is blessed with natural endowment of mineral resources. Most of the industrials of our Nigerian i state were solely established and wholly financed by the state. Some where established by subsequent governments. On each case, the general aims of establishing the industries have been to industrialize the state, provide employment opportunities to indigenes and general public. And also to improve the economy of the state by generating revenue.

Therefore, following the creation of Ebonyi state in Ist, October, 1996, some of the government owned industries

were jointly owned by the eastern regions states namely: Anambra, Cross River, Imo, Akwa Ibom, Enugu and Abia. It was after the creation of Ebonyi state in 1996 that some state like Ebonyi state inherited some of the government owned industries located in their state or areas, where as some industries were jointly owned by the neighboring state such industries are Ezzangbo building materials, Nkaliki hatchery farm, Nigeria cement company limited Nkalagu. etc.

Ezzangbo block industry as the major study of this work was established on 30th March 1987. However, the creation of ebonyi state in October 1st, 1996 changed its ownership status as the company management was handled over to the Ebonyi state government.

The industry was first formed partnership with an Israelites firm called “Diezengort West Africa limited”. The firm has been managed by seven different managers .The company produces different products used for building, construction of bridge etc. Some of its products are kings culverts of different sizes, concrete electric pole, blocks of different shapes, high tension poles etc.

However, the industry have been facing some problems which ranges from inadequacy of infrastructural facilities, lack of experience, poor record keeping, inadequate planning, wrong location, lack of de-lega-obsolete equipment ,lack of delegation of power, poor trained personnel, etc.

➤ *Statement of the Problem*

This project was undertaken to ascertain the degree of problems facing government owned industries in Ebonyi state with particular reference to Ezzangbo building materials industry Abakaliki. However, investigations carried out by Ezeani (2006) have shown that most public enterprises, especially in the developing countries such as Nigeria are seen as instrument for private wealth accumulation by the managers.

Industries are usually faced with some problems which usually affect their smooth running and progress. These problems ranges from inadequacy of infrastructural facilities, lack of experience, poor record keeping, inadequate planning, wrong location absolute equipment etc. Ezzangbo building materials is one of the industries in Ebonyi State which their progress has been so stagnant.

The general aim of this project is to investigate in a simple and clear manner which of the above listed problems affects “Ezzangbo building materials” which is the core topic of this work. It is worthy to mention that most of the crisis which these industries witnessed occur since the creation of Ebonyi State up till date.

➤ *Purpose of study*

The purpose of this research work is to investigate the problems facing government owned industries in Nigeria , with particular reference to Ezzangbo building materials. Specifically, the study intend to:

1. Determine the major problems facing government owned industries in Nigeria
2. Ascertain the managerial problems affecting government owned industries in Nigeria.
3. Determine the operational problems affecting the production process of Ezzangbo building materials.

➤ *Research Questions*

1. How does managerial problems affect government owned industries in Nigeria?
2. what are the technical problems affecting government owned industries.?
3. What are the operational problems affecting the production process of Ezzangbo building materials?

II. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

➤ *Definition of Management*

Obayi(1998),defined management as a group of people who coordinate the resources of man, money and materials through the process of planning, organizing, directing and controlling in order to achieve the organizational objectives. He said that to the student, management is a field of study or an academic discipline. Oduma (2004) saw management as the process of planning, organizing and controlling. Ejiofor (1984) in Nwosu (2002:3) defined management as “the art or science of working in an organization through being directed, and by directing and coordinating the activities of people to achieve one’s personal goals in the content of the goal of one’s organization.

Ezeaku(1983) in oduma (2004:106) opined that management meant getting things done through other people by organizing them into a work and assigning functions and ensuring through coordination, control and proper motivation. He further stated that the management is a function while manager is a person performing the function. Kast and Rosenewieg (1982) saw management as the coordination of human and material resources towards objective accomplishment which Akpala (1995.5) defined management as “the process of combing and utilizing or allocating an organization’s input (men, materials and money) by planning, organizing, directing and controlling for the purpose of producing output (goods and services or whatever the objectives are) desired by customers so that the organization objectives are achieved.

However, management is defined by Peter Drucker as the organ of society specifically charged with making resources productive.

In support to the above definitions, Nwosu (1996) posited that management means the art of science of using available resources (ie the four(4) m’s of management, man, money, materials and machines) to achieve stipulated goals. Nwosu further stated that how efficiency managers achieve these goals using the available resources would depend on the skill in planning, organizing, actuating and controlling the activities of an enterprises and mobilizing and motivating the work force.

➤ *Definition of Industry*

Industry is a term that has been viewed differently by different writers, but all boils to the same meaning.

Alfred (2009)defined industry as a group of companies that operate in the same segment of the economy or share a similar business type.

Okeke (1994) defined an industry as a group of firms producing similar product. He further stated that an industry may be of any size, it could be large or small, irrespective of the size (large or small) a carefully established industry should be properly managed to attain its set goals or objectives.

Aloke (2001) saw an industry as a business or sector that came together with the purpose of producing similar product with the objective of maximizing profit and minimizing lost.

According to Okeke (1974) industrialization is the process of building up a country’s productive capacity to process raw-materials and manufacture goods and services for consumption and further production. It also included the provision of basic needs such as water transport service within the country such that people will satisfy most of their basic needs, gainful employment and self-reliance. When country activities all the above mentioned, it is considered an industrialized country. Ezzangbo building materials produces concrete electric poles rings culvert of different size, blocks of different shape and sizes, high tension poles etc. just to meet up with the need of the state and their welfare services

➤ *Historical Background of Ezzangbo Building Materials*

Ezzangbo building materials was established in the year 1987 and was managed by the first General manager Engr.p.o Ndudinanti. Between 1987-1991, in the then old Anambra state. Then, came Engr. Marthin Itumo who managed the industry between 1991-1993 when Enugu state was created. After the tenure of Engr. Martin Itumo, there was no other manager appointed to continue the administration of the industry and the industry started having managerial problems until 1996 when Ebonyi state was created. However, Eng. K.C.Ozina was appointed to manage the industry from 1996-1998. then Engr. Aja Enyi managed the establishment between 2004 -2005. lastly Mr.

Emmanuel .E ODO is the present manager appointed to mae the industry from 2005 till date

➤ *Major Problems Facing Government Owned Industries*

Problem are those things that harmers or effect some things from functioning well. Therefore government owned industries has the following factors militating against its functioning

1. Inadequacy of Infrastructural Facilities:- Any industry that exists without the required facilities is bound to encounter a lot of difficulties.
Okafor and Ama (2005) saw water, electricity, accessible roads and means of communication as some of the facilities that affects the efficient performance of business.
2. Lack of experience:- Okafor and Ama (2005) referred to experience as business knowledge acquired over the years. Igwe (2007) observed that those who enter fields in which they have no experience have extremely slim chance of survival. For instance, majority of the workers in Ezzamgbo building materials lack the required experience for the industry.
3. 3.Poor record keeping: This is another problem faced by Ezzamgbo building materials. Some industries believed that the maintenance of books of account and other business records costly and unnecessary. Thus, the General manager gave a report concerning the industry (2003) which stated that some people felt that keeping proper records will be a source of exposing industry secrets to others.
This, prevent the banks from knowing the financial status of the industry. Hence they would find it difficult to get loan from the banks or any organization that could render such help.
4. Neglect:- This is a situation where by the owners of an industry or managers fail to cater for the main thing that would promote the industry rather focuses on other things that does not facilitate the affairs of the industry.
Okafor and Ama (2005) opined that involvement in politics as some of the causes of neglect. The government of Ebonyi state concentrate more in the business of politics rather than the affairs of the industries.
5. Inadequate planning:- The success of any business or industry depends on how well are they able to plan. According to Nwosu (2002)planning is the process of establishing and clarifying objectives, determining the policies and procedures necessary to realize the objectives and preparing a plan of action. Igwe (2007) observed that planning is critical to the success of any business. Ikekwoaba (2007) defined planning as a guide to an action. Consequently, the industry suffered problem of inadequacy of planning.
6. Poor /wrong location:- The location of industry is usually done with regard to some factors liken nearness to source of power, raw material and market. Igwe (2007) observed that too often, business locations are selected without proper study, investigation and planning. Block industry, Ezzamgbo is faced with these problems which contributes to its set backs.

7. Obsolete equipment when majority of equipment in an industry is almost wearing out, the industry will suffer a lot of set backs. Ezzamgbo block industry has a lot of equipment which are not functional. A worker in the industry called Eze Martin observed that the problems that they are having in the industry is that majority of the equipment are worn out.

According to Eze, other problems include:-

1. financial problem
2. workers poor attitude to work
3. lack of skilled man power.

➤ *Managerial Problems of Government Owned Industries.*

Management is the bed rock of the functionality of any industry or organization.

Therefore, when management problems occurs in an industry, the industry will suffer a lot of set backs. Scholars have been giving different definitions of management.

According to Nwosu (2002), management is the art or science of using available resources, that is, men, money, material and machine to achieve stipulated goals. In another development, Obayi (1998) defined management as a group of people who coordinate the resources man, money and materials through the process of planning, organizing, directing and controlling in order to achieve the organizational objectives. Oduma (2004) in his own view saw management as the process of planning, organizing and controlling.

According to Ikekwoaba (2007) management is the act of organizing scorehuman and material resources in order to achieve organizations objectives. Drunker (1974) view management as the organ of society specially charged with making resource productive.

Due to the comp lenity of the management function, Ezzamgbo building materials is faced with a lot of managerial problems.

Ezeani (2006) opined that some crisis particularly from public administration, tradition, argue that the new public management lack some of good aspects of the old model, high ethical standard , services to the state.

Ndoh and Emezi (1997) suggested that in every administration, the chief executive and accounting officer must be ready to give account of men and material, money as well as performance.

However, Drunker (1967) in Okpata (2004) summarized that an effective leader does right things, produces creative, alternatives, optimizes utilization, obtains results, increase profit and achieves objectives” He further stated that the concept of personnel management in Nigeria, call for skill in management and change. The personnel manager is required to be a specialist with adequate training, knowledge and experience so as to be able to provide top management, functional and line managers in the work

organization. This can be attributed to the wrong selection method resulting to unqualified appointee who may not have knowledge of effective leadership styles, motivation and effective utilization of available material.

The managerial problems of government owned industries can be attributed to the following.

1. Lack of delegation of power –: Obadan (2000) in Ezeani (2006) opines that public enterprise manager suffer from excessive control and interference in their daily operations by supervising government department. Most Management Centralize all power within themselves. Many enterprises particularly the large utility undertaking are reluctant to delegate authority and consequently will be inefficiency in performance.
2. Poor trained personnel; It is because many of the managers are poorly trained and lacking experience, they are neither motivated nor do they know what it takes to motivate the employees. Ezeani (2005) suggested that, it is therefore, difficult, if not impossible, for any government to perform these enormous tasks without the assistance and cooperation of the civil service.
3. Poor supervision:- Poor supervision is practiced in every department and the supervision is most unwilling to manage. It is because the right people are in a wrong place. I know that some are successful, well trained, physician, engineers, school teachers etc. but what is the fact is that they have not had a formal training and retraining in management.
4. Chronic Debt of NEPA and staff:- Eze a staff in the industry during an oral interview observed that most of the time, workers are not regularly paid, which resulted to un commitment and undedicated to their duties. Staff promotions is also delayed. Power supply is not reliable in Ezzamgbo building materials because of the chronic debt owing to the NEPA.

➤ *Financial Problems Affecting Government Owned Industries:*

Finance is the major actor in the smooth running of any organization, According to Okafor and Ama (2005) financial connotes money and monetary affairs of a person, an organization or a state.

Industry needs capital for the operation and growth of the industry. With regard to financial issue of an industry, Okefor and Ama (2005) had all these to say.

For business enterprises just as for individuals and countries, finance represents a fundamental resource. Fund is needed for instance, to purchase plants and equipment, furniture, building, raw-materials as well as for the payment of employees and the fulfillment of other obligations with the aid of finance, accumulated savings are either ploughed back into a business or channeled into other productive investment. According to Igwe (2007) under capitalization is a frequent total error leading to business failure. Therefore, Ezzamgbo building materials has suffered a lot set back due to lack of fund. There is no money to fully

reactivate the four lines of production, repair the factor, building, store building and re-rooting of the administrative block and canteen house that are leaking. Some of the machines are so aged that breakdown is always the order of the day. So, the industry needs money for replacement of some machines.

In a related development , Okefor and Ama (2005) further observed that research into the failure of business has identified two major causes which included poor financing and poor financial management .

In our modern world, it is not possible to separate business and finance. This proves the utility of fund to industries and organizations. Government owned industries just as the Ezzamgbo building materials is not well fund or neglected by the government of Ebonyi state. In another development, the finance that is put in the industry is not well managed. This has been the problem faced by the industry in area of finance.

➤ *Technical Problems Affecting Government owned Industries*

According to Oxford advanced learners dictionary, technical is connected with the practical use of machinery, methods etc.

In science and industry, Technical is the practical application of science and technology during production. In any industry that engage in the production of any particular product, there must exist some technicality. Therefore, some industries may be faced with some technical problems during production which may or must effect their production process and their out put at large.

Ezzamgbo building materials is faced with some of these problems that effected they level of out-put. In an oral interview with a worker in the industry, Mr. Martin Eze, was of the view that the technical problems they experience ia as a result of competency and lack of sufficient raw-material.

Due to lack of fund to employ competent workers, those employed are not technical enough to over come the technical problems. More so, the lack of sufficient raw-material worse the situation since they try to manage the few ones they. In a similar development, the number of blocks , poles and convert rings destroyed are usually very much. This is attributed to wrong use of machinery etc. Furthermore, during load and off loading of these products, some destruction is also experienced. This is due to the fact that those in charge are not competent enough as wrong means due to the nature of the vehicle. Those who engage in the mixture and measurement of sand, cement, and concrete is not left out. They at time use wrong measurement or do not mix them very well. The operators of the machines, plants and equipment are not left out since at times they disappoint the industry, there by hindrance production.

➤ *Operational Problems Affecting the Production Process of Industries*

Production process is the various stages that raw-material has to under go before making available a finished product or the act of making goods ready for use or the systematic steps that is involved in making goods available for use. Those things that pose a threat to production during production process is referred to as operational problems

Ezeani (2006) summarized that the deteriorating state of infrastructure in most of African countries also contributes to the high cost of operation. Operational technical problems of the industry arises from staff management and government poor attitude towards the industry. For instance, Ezzamgbo block industry have only two operational vehicles that is road worth or useful out of the ten vehicles for operational services. While the rest of the vehicles are parked on unhelpfully. This makes quick delivery of their products very difficult. According to Eze Martin in an oral interview, power outage is usually a threat to production process. In this view, at times when production is going on, power failure usually distort the production process. More so, the deteriorating nature threat to production process. There are also shortage of raw-material during production. All these are attributed to lack of fund.

However, government on their own parts do not see the industry, especially government owned industries as an asset rather regards them especially the one understudy, Ezzamgbo block industry as liabilities instead of investment huge amount of money and develop the industry.

➤ *Steps in solving Managerial Problems in Industries*

According to Nwachukwu (1988) management is the guidance or direction of people towards organizational objectives. It can also be seen as the supervising; controlling and coordinating of activity as to attain optimum with organizational resources. According to Nwosu (2002) as cited in his book, management in the modern content comprises the coordinated performance of the five specific managerial functions of planning, organizing, staffing, directing and controlling. From these definition of management, the steps in solving managerial problems can be derived. Some of the solutions includes:-

1. Recruitment and training of personnel/staff:- This entails that for the managerial problems to be solved, there should be proper training of staff and personnel on the competences need by the industry.
2. Regular supervision :- There should be regular supervision of the activities of the managers by government agencies to ensure that every thing is going normal.
3. Delegation of authority or power :- Delegation of authority is the process where by an executive gives a subordinate power to perform duty on behalf of him. This is done when the executives has too much work or in his absence. When this is done, the industry will be carried along and progress assured.
- 4.

5. proper Record-Keeping:- Record shows both the financial status and progress of an industry. The management should ensure that proper record is kept because if not, a lot of damages will be observed. To this end, Chukwu (2004) opined that, the poor accounting records on small scale business will not help the manager to determine the financial position of the business. Also, Igboke (2004) was of the view that the profit or loss of a business must be accurately measured if only good accounting records must be kept.

➤ *Review of Related Empirical Study*

Akochi (2002) carried out a research on problems and prospects of public enterprises in Nigeria using Ezzamgbo building materials as a case study in Ebonyi State. Questionnaire was the major instrument used for data collection. The population of the study was 125 workers in the industry which 100 workers was randomly sampled for the study. The following findings were revealed in the study.

1. Lack of qualified staff of the industry:- That is to say, the majority of the staff in the industry were FSLC and WAEC holders.
2. The study also revealed that poor accounting record were experienced in government owned industry.
3. Poor training and retraining of staff also contributed to the industry's problem. Also, Okoro (2001) carried out a survey research on the management problems of government owned industries in Ebonyi State, using Nkaliki hatchery farm as a case study.

Questionnaire was the major instrument used for data collection. The population of the study was 400 workers in the industry in which 200 workers were randomly sampled for the study. The following findings were discovered in the industry:

1. Lack of finance to carry out developmental projects.
2. Unprompted payment of workers' salary which resulted to absenteeism to work.
3. Insecurity of staff and their equipment within the work premises.
4. Lack of qualified staff employed into the industry.
5. Poor maintenance of tools also militates against its management.

➤ *Summary of literature Review*

The literature reviewed so far have been able to identify the major problems faced by government owned industries in Ebonyi State, which the Ezzamgbo materials also experienced, that resulted to its retrogression.

The concept of industry was reviewed by different people in different ways but all boiled to the fact that it engaged in production of goods.

However, the major problems facing government owned industries were seen. Government neglect is some of the problems, funding, poor record-keeping, inadequate infrastructural facilities, lack of experience were some of the major problems identified.

Managerial problems of industries were also reviewed which included among others: lack of delegation of power, poor supervision. The financial problems of government owned industries were reviewed which poor funding and poor financial management were identified as the major causes of business failure. During production, there are some operational problems like power outage, few workable vehicle, shortage of raw materials etc, were observed as some of the operational problems.

The steps in solving managerial problems were also reviewed which proper record keeping delegation of authority, regular supervision and recruitment and training of staff/personnel were identified as the solutions. The review of related empirical studies were also done in relation to the present study.

III. METHODOLOGY

➤ *Design*

The design of this study is a survey research design.

➤ *Area of the Study*

Area of the study is Ezzamgbo building materials, Abakaliki in Ebonyi State.

Population of the study

➤ *Population of the Study*

The population for the study consisted of all the 120 workers in Ezzamgbo block industry. (source staff normal roll Ezzamgbo block industry)

➤ *Sample and Sampling Techniques*

Sample and sampling techniques used the entire population for the study. There was no sample because the population manageable size was also sampling.

➤ *Instrument for Data Collection*

The instrument used for data collection was structured questionnaire. The questionnaire comprised of two sections; section “A” and section “B” section “A” elicit information on personal data while section “B” dealt with the main research questions for the study. Section B further consisted of five (5) sub-question. Each sub-section each of dealt with specific research question. Each sub- section is made up of four (4) items questions and total of (20) questionnaire items were used. A modified tinker rating scale was used. A modified tikert rating scale was to seek for responses to them from the respondents.

➤ *Method of Data Collection*

The questionnaire was designed and administered by hand to the 120 staff of Ezzamgbo block industry in Abakaliki , Ebonyi state in order to elicit information on the problems of government owned industries in Ebonyi state. Some of the questionnaires was personally administered and collected by the clerical officers and receptionists of the industry. This is to enable the researcher reach the staff who do not go to work every day.

➤ *Method of Data Analysis*

The research used a statistical mean in the analysis and interpretation of data collected on a 4 point Likert scale.

➤ *Data Presentation and Analysis*

The data collected was presented and analyzed using mean statistics. This was done using mean (x) in accordance with the five (5) research questions and was based on the one hundred and twenty (120) respondents who all filled and returned their questionnaires.

Research question 1

What are the major problems facing government owned industries in Ebonyi State?

In the questionnaire, item 1 to 4 were designed to solicit the response of the respondents to the research question above. Their responses were shown in the table below.

Table 1:- the mean (x) scores of major problems facing government owned industries in Nigeria.
Mean Scores of Major Problems of Government Owned Companies

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	N	FX	X	Decision
1	Financial constraint is one of the major problems facing government owned industries.	58	36	17	9	120	383	3.2	Accepted
2	Inadequate infrastructural facilities is a problem to government owned industries.	53	40	11	16	120	370	3.1	Accepted
3	Neglect by the government is a problem to government owned industries. management styles poses a problem to government owned industries	49	52	10	9	120	381	3.2	Accepted
4.	Some tension for greater productivity	35	41	25	19	120	332	2.7	Accepted

➤ **Results**

From the data presented in table 1 above, it was revealed that questionnaire items 1,2,3,and 4 scored above 2.5 mean (x) cut off point. These items recorded mean (x) scores of 3.2,3.2 and 2.7 respectively. This reveals that all items 1,2,3 and 4 were all accepted with no rejection by the respondents. Consequently, it is an indication that the items were all accepted by the respondents as the major problems facing government owned industries in Nigeria

Research Question 1

How does managerial problem affect government owned industries in Nigeria?

To answer this research question, item 5 to 8 of the questionnaire were designed to seek information from the respondents. The table below reveals their responses.

Table 2:- mean (x) scores on how managerial problem affect government owned industries in Ebonyi state.

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	N	FX	X	Decision
5	Poor supervision of the activities of the industry due to managerial laxity.	42	45	22	11	120	358	2.9	Accepted
6	Managerial problems leads to lack of delegation of authority by the management	23	30	25	42	120	244	2.3	Accepted
7	Lack of incentives to workers	51	38	19	12	120	368	3.1	Rejected
8	Poorly trained personnel in the industry leads to inefficiency	37	44	22	17	120	341	2.8	Accepted

➤ **Results**

In the table above, items, 5,7,and 8 received mean (x-) score of 2.9, 3.1 and 2.8 respectively which are all above the cut off mean (x-) of 2.9 , 3.1 and 2.8 respectively which are all above the cut off mean (x-) of 2.5.

This reveals that the items were accepted by the respondents as how managerial problems affect government owned industries in Ebonyi State.

On the other hand, item 6 of the questionnaire was rejected by the respondents as how managerial problems

affect owned industries in Ebonyi State. This is because it recorded a mean (x-) score of 2.3 which is below the cut off mean (x-) point of 2.5.

Research question 2

What are the technical problems affecting Ezzangbo block industry?

Questionnaire if 9 to 12 were designed to seek the opinion of the respondents on the research question above. Their responses were presented and analyzed using mean in the table below.

Table 3:- The mean (x-) scores of the technical problems affecting Ezzangbo block industry?

Questionnaire if 9 to 12 were designed to seek the opinion of the respondents on the research question above. Their responses were presented and analyzed using mean(x) in the table below

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	N	FX	X	Decision
9	Inferior spare parts affect good functioning of machines	39	43	20	18	120	343	2.8	Accepted
10	During loading and off loading, some products are destroyed	32	38	28	22	120	320	2.6	Accepted
11	Those who engage in mixture of sand, cement and concrete some times use wrong measurement/mixture	21	32	28	39	120	275	2.3	Accepted
12	Break down of plant machinery		80	38	84	295	772	2.6	Accepted

➤ **Results**

The data presented in table 3 above revealed that three (3) out of (4) items question were accepted by the respondents with the rejection of item ii. This is because they received mean (x-) score that are above 2.5 the cut off mean (x-) point. The are above 2.5 the cut off with mean(x-) scores of 2.8, 2.6 and 2.9 respectively and were therefore accepted by the respondents as the technical problems affecting Ezzangbo block industry.

Item ii as noted earlier were rejected by respondents because it had mean (x-) point of 2.3 which is below the cut off mean (x-) point of 2.5 .

Therefore it is rejected by the respondents as a technical problem affecting Ezzangbo block industry.

Research question 3

What are the operational problems affecting the production process of Ezzangbo block industry?

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	N	FX	X	Decision
17	Government agencies seldom supervise the activities of the managers.	36	41	22	21	120	332	2.8	Accepted
18	The government recruits and trains staff	35	33	29	23	120	320	2.6	Accepted
19	The government has stated all her industries for privatization and for poor performance	16	28	45	31	120	269	2.2	Rejected
20	The government appoints competent managers.	43	30	21	26	120	330	2.8	Accepted

Table 4

IV. FINDINGS

Table 4 above shows that questionnaire items 13, 14, 15, and 16 had mean (x) scores of 2.9, 2.7, 2.7 and 2.6 respectively. These items were all accepted because they all had mean (x) scores that are above the cut off mean (x) point of 2.5. This is an indication that the respondents accepted all the items as the operation process of Ezzangbo block industry with no rejection.

Research question 1

How managerial problems affect government owned industry in Ebonyi State?

Based on the research carried out under the research question: how does managerial problems affect government owned industries in Ebonyi State? The researcher observed that only item 6 was rejected by the respondents out of the 4 items questions which ranged from 5 to 8 under the above research question. The researcher based on the responses of the respondents and opined that poor supervision of the industry due to managerial laxity, lack of incentives to workers and poorly trained personnel in the industry leads to inefficiency as how managerial problems affect Ezzangbo block industry.

In laying credence to this findings, Gurum (2004) stated that most business failed due to the lack of professional assistance and managerial principles. These managerial principles refers to those poor supervision, lack of incentives and poorly trained personnel in the industry.

Research question 2

Technical problems affecting Ezzangbo block industry. The data presented and analyzed in table iii focused on research question: what are the technical problems affecting Ezzangbo block industry? The findings under this research question showed that item 9, 10 and 12 was accepted by the respondents as the technical problems affecting Ezzangbo block industry. Consequently, the finding revealed that inferior spare parts affect good functioning machines, during loading and off loading, some products are destroyed and break down of plant and machinery are the technical problems affecting Ezzangbo block industry. To further buttress this finding a worker in the industry Marthin Eze was of the view that the technical problem they are experiencing was as a result of competency and lack of raw

materials. This competency calls for the destruction of some products during loading and offloading. Lack of raw material is attributed to inferior spare parts.

Research question 3:

The operational problems affecting the production process of Ezzangbo block industry. The result of the data presented in the table iv dealt with the research question : what are the production process of Ezzangbo block industry? The study revealed that the respondents accepted all the four (4) item questions of the questionnaire the respondents there fore accepted that power outage, articulated vehicle, deteriorating nature of plant and machinery and poor operating skills of machinery in the industry are the operational problems that affects production process of Ezzangbo block industry. To support this finding, Ezeani (2006) was of the view that deteriorating state of the infrastructure in most African countries also contributes to the failure of public enterprises as they contributes to the high cost of production. Eze Marthin also stressed on the issue of power outage in competencies of machine and plant operators and lack of vehicle for delivery.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In view of the research findings and discussion made into obvious that the problem of industry if properly addressed will make change in the activities of the industry which will bring positive results. If the problem of funding, infrastructure and management is properly handled, things will work well in the industry.

More so, if the workers in the industry properly paid, there should be supervision of activities of the managers to avoid misappropriation of funds. That is why Chukwu (2004) suggested that proper accounting records is now considered to be tool of management , providing vital information concerning the future of business entry . further more , the industry suffers because of the use of out data plants and machines. There is also constant power outage which its issue should be addressed. The in competency of workers in the industry also cause a lot of problem and also should be addressed.

The managerial problems which the government is trying to solve requires serious attention so that the activities of the industry should be well coordinated.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings made in this study, the following recommendations were made by the researcher.

1. The government should provide financial assistance to the industry.
2. The government should not only concentrate on politics but also pay attention to the activities of the industry.
3. Government agencies should supervise the activities of the industry.
4. The government should consider the option of privatizing the industry if he cannot take care of it.
5. the outdated plants and machines should be replaced with new ones
6. the government should also recruit and train competent workers for the industry.

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